

ROLE OF FORGIVENESS ON LIFE SATISFACTION AMONG COLLEGE STUDENTS

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Abstract: The present investigation was intended to ascertain the relationship between forgiveness and life satisfaction among college students. The sample of the study consisted of 240 college students. The forgiveness Heartland scale (HFS) made by Thompson, Snyder, Lesa Hoffman, Scott, Heather, Laura Billings, Laura Heinze, Jason, Hal Shorey, Jessica, Danae, (2005) with the subscale of self-forgiveness, forgiving others, and forgiving situations, and Satisfaction with Life Scale (SWLS) developed by Diener, Emmons, Larsen, and Griffin (1985) were used for the data collection. Pearson's product moment correlation was applied to study the relationship among forgiveness, and life satisfaction. T-test was applied for the study of mean difference between male and female. Findings shows that forgiveness with its three dimensions (i.e. self-forgiveness, forgiving others, and forgiving situations) positively correlated with life satisfaction. It means that when forgiveness will increase life satisfaction also will increase and vice-versa.

Keywords: Forgiveness, Life satisfaction and College Students.

1. INTRODUCTION

Rational and background of the study

As per sample of the study is concerned, college students were selected. This period of life is comparatively more enthusiastic and the extreme point of the zeal. They spend more time to achieve their satisfaction by several resources available in the society/around them.

The key variable of this study is *life satisfaction*, which is subjective and varied from person to person. It means that some people may feel satisfied with their life by achieving materialistic things while others may experience satisfaction by relationships. Still there may be some similarities in both the individuals to achieve the goal (satisfaction with life). There are number of factors might affect life satisfaction, out of them forgiveness also play an important role of the some extent. As we know that maladjustment leads to anxiety followed by frustration in life that is why one has to balance health, family, emotional, social as well as educational adjustment to avoid unease. Similarly, we as human being sometimes commit mistakes and more often our elders, teachers and friends as well forgive for that because they might feel pleasure by doing so. Likewise, sometimes we also avoid our younger's mistakes; in fact such types of activities strengthen our relationship with each other. The good relationship with family members, friends, neighbors, teachers and colleagues is also very important for the satisfaction. Self-forgiveness, forgiveness to others, and forgiveness to situations as well are factors may lead to satisfaction. Taking all these things into consideration life satisfaction in relation to forgiveness decided to study among college students.

Statement of the Problem

Topic of the present study is "*Role of Forgiveness on Life Satisfaction among College Students*" Life satisfaction is the most important for every age group where tendency of forgiveness play a major role in it.

Forgiveness

Forgiveness is the intentional and voluntary process by which a victim undergoes a change in feelings and attitude regarding an offense, let's go of negative emotions such as vengefulness, with an increased ability to wish the offender well (APA, 2006).

As a psychological concept and virtue, the benefits of forgiveness have been explored in religious thought, the social sciences and medicine. Forgiveness may be considered simply in terms of the person who forgives (Graham & Michael, 2014) including forgiving themselves, in terms of the person forgiven or in terms of the relationship between the forgiver and the person forgiven. In most contexts, forgiveness is granted without any expectation of restorative justice, and without any response on the part of the offender (for example, one may forgive a person who is incommunicado or dead). In practical terms, it may be necessary for the offender to offer some form of acknowledgment, an apology, or even just ask for forgiveness, in order for the wronged person to believe himself able to forgive (APA, 2006).

The systematic study of the effects of forgiveness, especially within the social sciences, has been relatively brief. Moreover, the initial body of literature that was produced was replete with disputes regarding the best way to define the construct. As a result, investigators have characterized forgiveness in dissimilar ways (McCullough, 2001). For instance, depending on which research team is involved in the study, forgiveness has been conceptualized as either a cognitive process, an emotional process, a behavioral process, a motivational process, or some combination of these processes (Tsang, McCullough & Fincham). Although some disagreements remain, a general consensus has recently emerged and the literature now reflects a growing agreement among researchers

Researchers who study forgiveness tend to concur that the process of forgiveness is a challenging undertaking, which requires a move away from negative inter and intra-personal reactions, towards more positive ones (Lin, Enright & Klatt, 2011). Interpersonal disputes and disagreements are a normative component of the human experience. In response to these negatively-charged situations, the process of forgiveness begins with a complete awareness that the transgressor is culpable for the transgression. Hence, the victim is entitled to feel anger, and correspondingly, under no obligation to feel any compassion towards the transgressor (Fincham, 2000). However, the willingness to forgive helps individuals overcome interpersonal conflicts by deliberately letting-go of the resentment and anger that often follows an offense (Hansen, Enright, Baskin, & Klatt, 2009). Being in a state of "unforgiveness" is marked by sentiments such as anger, hostility, resentment, bitterness, and shame (Harris & Thoresen, 2005). However, forgiveness can be seen as one possible alternative to unforgiveness, which enables a shift away from the potentially difficult and detrimental feelings associated with unforgiveness. Therefore, forgiveness, unlike unforgiveness, helps bring about more favorable, constructive feelings that generally have more positive connotations (Worthington, 2004). Finally, most researchers also agree that forgiveness is not purely a dichotomous decision, where an individual either does or does not forgive.

Researchers appear to be reaching some consensus regarding what forgiveness is, but more consistently, researchers are able to agree upon what forgiveness is not (Miller, Worthington & McDaniel, 2008). Although forgiveness has the potential to engender the repair of a damaged relationship, forgiveness is not reconciliation (Fincham, 2000). Reconciliation implies an overt behavioral rejoining of two separated parties, whereas forgiveness is an internal response to a perceived injury. As such, it is possible to forgive without reconciliation. For example, an individual can forgive a transgressor even if it is impossible to physically restore the relationship, as is the case if the transgressor is deceased or incarcerated. Also, an individual can forgive a transgressor even if he or she has no desire to restore the relationship, as is the case if the transgressor was an abusive partner (McCullough, Bono & Root, 2005). Moreover, a reunion of a once-severed relationship does not imply that forgiveness has occurred. A victim and a transgressor may reunify for various reasons, such as loneliness or financial hardship, where the victim remains unforgiving. Additionally, forgiveness does not necessarily imply acceptance or pardon. Instead, the forgiver cultivates beneficial responses such as compassion and empathy, while suspending destructive responses that may terminate relationships (Enright, 1992). A forgiver may continue to disapprove of the initial offense indefinitely.

Though there is no universally accepted "gold-standard" definition of forgiveness, there is certainly some level of agreement among investigators. Perhaps forgiveness is best understood as a latent variable, or an amalgamation of various processes that work together and cannot be directly observed in isolation (Svalina & Webb, 2012). Indisputably, forgiveness is a multifaceted and complex construct, which has been examined both philosophically and empirically from various angles. Different aspects of forgiveness have been delineated, highlighting unique dimensions of the process of forgiveness, which include the state/trait and inter/intrapersonal distinction.

Life Satisfaction

Life satisfaction is a psychological construct that enables an individual to use selected standards to cognitively evaluate his or her life (Diener, Suh, Lucas, & Smith, 1999). For the purpose of this study, life satisfaction and psychosocial well-being are used interchangeably.

Fujita and Diener (2005) argue that most people demonstrate long-term stability of life satisfaction. This research has practical importance in the field of psychology because of its impact on life satisfaction of the aging.

Studies show mixed results in examining the relationship of life satisfaction with age (Mroczek & Spiro, 2005). Aging is a complex series of physical, psychological, and social changes. Successful aging can be determined by life satisfaction, defined as a mirror of life (Caspi & Elder, 1986). While some researchers label life satisfaction a precursor of successful aging, others such as Caspi and Elder (1986) define successful aging as life satisfaction. However, life satisfaction is just one part of the socio-psychological model (Bowling, 2007). Although successful aging depends on a number of factors, many models are one-dimensional and lack empirical research (Bowling, 2007). While healthy lifestyles and other precursors of well-being are underestimated, predictors of life satisfaction in aging adults can be seen years and perhaps decades earlier. The definition of life satisfaction, social scientists say, comes from a subjective perspective (Diener, 1984).

Concept of life satisfaction

Satisfaction is a state of mind. It is an evaluative appraisal of something. The term refers to both 'contentment' and 'enjoyment'. As such it covers cognitive-as well as affective-appraisals. Satisfaction can be both evanescent and stable through time (Veenhoven, Scherpenzeel & Bunting, 1996).

As most human beings try to be happy in life, life satisfaction can be assumed to be a widely shared goal of humanity. Generally, being satisfied with life means having a favorable attitude toward one's life as a whole (Haybron, 2007, p. 2), implying "a global evaluation by the person of his or her life" (Pavot, Diener, Colvin, & Sandvik, 1991, p. 150). Economically speaking, life satisfaction represents a personal utility that individuals strive for, thus organizations and policy-makers need to be aware of its dynamics and how their actions impact it (Fennell, 1991). It is characteristic for this line of research that subjective rather than objective criteria of life quality are judged, so as to capture "true" personal satisfaction.

Life satisfaction is one of the most important issues of the present scenario. Evidences show that life satisfaction can reproduce experiences that have influenced a person in a positive way. These experiences have the ability to motivate people to pursue and reach their respective goals.

Lyubomirsky (2001) in his definition of life satisfaction stated it in terms of mental assessment of an individual's life quality, which has cognitive component and is counted as powerful anticipant of mental health. Life satisfaction is in fact satisfaction of all spheres of life (Sousa and Lyubomirsky, 2001). Life dissatisfaction disregarding its causes has many negative consequences. Life dissatisfaction is related to poor health status, depression symptoms, personality problems, poor health behaviors and poor social conditions (Bahreinian & Yavari Kermani, 2009).

Life satisfaction, in general, represents personal satisfaction about his/her own life (Telman & Ünsal 2004). Life satisfaction shows the result of comparison of personal expectations and reality. When we use the term "life satisfaction", we understand a general satisfaction, not about a specific event (Ozdevecio ğlu and Aktas 2007).

Importance of the present study

Through this study researcher try to know about how much college students are satisfied with their lives in terms of forgiveness tendency. Dissatisfaction with life take place followed by number of problems some of them they faced are maladjustment, anger, frustration, anxiety, depressions, emotional problems, mental wellbeing problems, stress, blaming themselves, isolation from the society, problems with relationship, decrease in social support, smoking and drugs consumption increasing etc. The person having forgiveness tendency may have better life satisfaction, because in many cases due to forgiveness people experience pleasure which is also a sign of satisfaction.

Objectives of the study

1. To study the relationship between forgiveness and life satisfaction.
2. To study the role of forgiveness on life satisfaction.
3. To study the mean difference of forgiveness and life satisfaction among male and female college students.

2. AIM OF REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Aim of the literature review in general focuses on context for the research, justifying the research, ensure the research hasn't been done before, highlight flaws in previous research, illustrate how the subject has been studied previously, outline gaps in previous researches and show that the work is adding to the understanding and knowledge of the field.

The related studies in any field forms the base upon which future work will depend. Literature review makes the sense of awareness with the previous researches that has been done. It also provides an opportunity of gaining insight into the method, measures, subject and approaches employed by the different researchers. A careful review of research sources of information about the problem to be investigated is one of the vital steps in the planning of any research. In the present study intention was to study the satisfaction level in correspondence with forgiveness among college students.

Forgiveness and life Satisfaction

Forgiveness is typically an inter and intra-personal task that requires a transition from negative emotions to more positive ones. The process of forgiveness often follows an interpersonal transgression, whereby the victim experiences some harm and is not required to forgive. Unforgiveness, another potential response to an interpersonal transgression, consists of delayed negative emotions such as hostility, hatred, anger and fear (Worthington & Scherer, 2004). Forgiveness includes the cultivation of beneficial responses, such as compassion and empathy, while also refraining from unforgiving responses that may terminate relationships. In other words, forgiveness involves letting go of the negative emotions associated with unforgiveness. Although much of the literature considers forgiveness to be a pro-social coping response that follows after an interpersonal injury, forgiveness can also follow after a myriad of perceived injuries, such as a loss of a loved one or a loss of a job (Luskin, Ginzburg & Thoresen, 2005). Regardless of the impetus, forgiveness can potentially lead to positive outcomes (Hansen, 2009). Specifically, research indicates that the ability to forgive is associated with psychological well-being and physical health (Lin, 2011). For example, higher levels of state and trait forgiveness have been associated with decreased symptoms of depression and anxiety; decreased physiological reactivity; and self-reported improvement in health and psychological well-being that is also an indicator of life satisfaction (e.g., McCullough, 2001).

Cornish and Wade (2015) conducted a specific research which suggests that the ability to genuinely forgive one's self can be significantly beneficial to an individual's emotional as well as mental well being.

The research indicates that the ability to forgive one's self for past offenses can lead to decrease feeling of negative emotions such as SHAME AND GUILT, and can increase the use of more positive practices such as self-kindness and self-compassion (Cornish and Wade, 2015).

In terms of relationships, forgiveness is related to increased commitment, satisfaction, and closeness (Bono et al., 2008; Maltby et al., 2005; McCullough, 2000). A study conducted by Ali Ayten, Hamza Ferhan (v) on forgiveness, religiousness, and life satisfaction in which they found that females scored higher in life satisfaction than males.

Although the relationship between forgiveness and well-being appears robust, few studies have examined the potential benefits of forgiveness in older adults. In general, there is a growing understanding that psychosocial factors can play an important role in improving physical and mental health outcomes in older adults (Krause & Ingersoll-Dayton, 2001).

Miller, Worthington, and McDaniel (2008) conducted 70 studies investigating the link between gender and forgiveness and found that females had a higher inclination towards forgiveness than males.

Finding of Algoe, Gable, & Maisel (2010) reveals that strengths such as gratitude and forgiveness help to nourish relationships. In addition to important benefits for wellbeing (see the positive emotions domain) gratitude has been found to be positively related to relationship satisfaction.

Empirical evidence suggests that individuals can learn to become more forgiving, and by doing so, can have a positive influence on their physical and mental health (Thorsen, Luskin & Harris, 1998). In addition, unforgiveness is linked with rumination, and rumination has been found to interfere with healthy coping and to aggravate chronic illnesses that affect older adults, such as heart disease and cancer (Baider & De-Nour, 1997). It is possible that brief education-based interventions for older adults could be developed; these treatments could generate awareness of and encourage forgiveness, which may result in more positive outcomes in older adults.

Studies show that people who forgive are happier and healthier than those who hold resentments (Campaign for Forgiveness Research, 2006). The first study to look at how forgiveness improve physical health discovered that when people think about forgiving an offender it leads to improved functioning in their cardiovascular and nervous system (Van Oyen, Witvilet, Ludwig and Vander Lann (2001). Another study conducted by Sarinopoulos (2000) at the University of Wisconsin found the more forgiving people were, the less they suffered from a wide range of illnesses. The less forgiving people reported a greater number of health problems.

Hypotheses of the study

1. There will be positive relationship between forgiveness and life satisfaction.
2. There will be positive role of forgiveness on life satisfaction.
3. There will be significant mean difference of forgiveness and life satisfaction among male and female college students.

3. METHODOLOGY

Methodology is considered as fundamental part of any research. It works as the most important element of the whole research. The absolute requirement of any type of social science research is to control, predict, describe and explain some sort of behavior. To explain the behavior we must need to observe which technique will be applied to get minute information about the behavior or phenomenon under study. Hence research should be conducted with eagerness to find out something new, and with a desire to add knowledge to the existing field, to identify the research gaps, and to analyze the findings in an unbiased manner to infer conclusion (Shontz, 1965; and Megargee, 1966).

Research Design

Research design defines the study type, research question/objectives, hypotheses, variables, and data collection methods. Some examples of research designs include descriptive, correlational, and experimental. Another distinction can be made between quantitative and qualitative methods ("Determining the Research Design." *Boundless Sociology*. Boundless, 08 Jan. 2016).

Present study is based on *correlational and predictive research design*. It aims to study about *Forgiveness as the predictor of Life Satisfaction*. Primary quantitative data was generated for the purpose of the study to empirically examine the research hypotheses and to meet the research objectives.

Inclusion Criteria

- Only the students of under graduate, post graduate and research scholars were taken as sample.
- Both male and female participants were included.
- No gender difference was made while selecting the sample.
- No discrimination was done on the basis of caste.
- Only the desired students were included in the sample.
- Participants were taken from Arts, Science and commerce streams.

Exclusion Criteria

- No High School or intermediate students were taken as sample.
- The students unwilling to take part in the study were not considered for this study.
- Even during the filling up of the questionnaires, if any participant wanted to leave, they were excluded.

Sample

Participants of the study consisted of 240 (graduate, post graduate and research scholars) college students. The sample was drawn through *convenient sampling* technique, from Aligarh Muslim University, Aligarh, Uttar Pradesh, India.

Tools Used

Heartland Forgiveness Scale (HFS)

This scale was made by Thompson et al. (2005) with the subscale of self-forgiveness, forgiving others, and forgiving situations. Participants were administered the HFS (Heartland Forgiveness Scale), an 18-items, self-report measure of dispositional forgiveness. It consists of three dimensions, six-items were in each subscales that measure forgiveness of self (items 1 to 6), forgiveness of others (items 7 to 12), and forgiveness of situations (items 13 to 18) respectively. Respondents indicate the extent to which each item is true or false to them using a 7-point scale with four verbal anchors: 15 Almost Always False of Me, 35 More Often False of Me, 55 More Often True of Me, and 75 Almost Always True of Me. The HFS total scale and subscale scores are calculated by summing the items on each scale, with the nine negatively worded items (2, 4, 6, 7, 9, 11, 13, 15, and 17) being reverse-scored.

In assessing the psychometric properties, Thomason, et al. (2005) reported Cronbach's Alpha for Forgiveness of Self as .75, Forgiveness of Others as .79, Forgiveness of Situations as .79 and Forgiveness of Total as .87; test-retest reliabilities were .72, .73, .77, and .83 respectively, with a three-week test-retest interval.

Satisfaction with Life Scale

The Satisfaction with Life Scale (SWLS) was first developed by Diener, Emmons, Larsen, and Griffin (1985) to measure cognitive self-evaluation of global life satisfaction. Then it was revised by Pavot and Diener (1993). It is a 5-item instrument designed to measure global cognitive judgments of satisfaction with one's life. Each item scored on a 7-point Likert scale, ranging from 1 (strongly disagree) to 7 (strongly agree). Scale scores range from 5-35, with higher scores indicating greater life satisfaction (7). Scores are categorized as extremely satisfied (31-35), satisfied (26-30), slightly satisfied (21-25), neutral (20), slightly dissatisfied (15-19), dissatisfied (10-14), and extremely dissatisfied (5-9).

Procedure

The respondents were approached individually and before administering the questionnaires good rapport established. Afterward they were asked to read the instructions carefully given on the questionnaires and give their responses to complete the questionnaires of Heartland Forgiveness Scale, and Satisfaction with Life Scale. Participants were taken 15 to 25 minutes to give their complete responses. All the respondents were told that their anonymity will be preserved and their responses will be confidential as well as used only for research purpose. Finally, with special thanks questionnaires were collected from them and scored manually.

Statistical Analysis

In order to meet the research objectives data were analyzed; Pearson's products moment correlation was administered to study the relationship between forgiveness and life satisfaction. Multiple regression was administered to study the role of forgiveness on life satisfaction. Further, t-test was applied to examine the mean differences between male and female as well as one way ANOVA was administered to examine the mean differences of different streams, qualification and different groups.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

First of all, Pearson Product Moment correlations were calculated in order to find out the relationship between predictor (forgiveness) and criterion (life satisfaction) variable among college students. At the second stage, the step-wise multiple linear regression analysis (SMRA) was undertaken in order to determine significant predictor of life satisfaction among college students.

Table 1: Inter-correlation matrix (Forgiveness and Life Satisfaction variables) (N=240).

Variables		Forgiveness				Life Satisfaction
		X1	X2	X3	X4	Y1
Forgiveness SS	X1	1	.002	.097	.696**	.189**
	X2		1	.267**	.468**	.204**
	X3			1	.467**	.133*
	X4				1	.171**
Life Satisfaction	Y1					1

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed), **. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed). X1=Self Forgiveness, X2=Others Forgiveness, X3=Situational Forgiveness, X4=Forgiveness Total, Y1=Life Satisfaction.

Table 1 showed that overall forgiveness and its dimensions (i.e. self-forgiveness, others forgiveness and situational forgiveness) were positively and significantly correlated with Life satisfaction. It means that as forgiveness increases life satisfaction also increases and vice-versa. Therefore, hypothesis “H1: There will be positive relationship between forgiveness and life satisfaction” is supported as probability to support the hypothesis was (p<0.01) level of significance. Finding indicated that as the level of forgiveness increases, life satisfaction also increases and vice-versa. Thus, it can be inferred that college students who experienced higher level of forgiveness will show higher level of life satisfaction in the true sense.

Further, the effect size for significant predictor variable was computed to estimate the magnitude or size of an effect on criterion variable. Cohen's f^2 is one of effect size measure was used in context of multiple regression analysis. Table 4.2 shows descriptions for magnitudes of f^2 as suggested by Cohen (1988). The formula used to calculate effect size (Cohen's f^2) is shown below:

$$f^2 = \frac{R^2}{1 - R^2}$$

Where, R^2 is the squared multiple correlation.

Table 2: Levels of effect-size

Effect Size	f^2
Small	0.02
Medium	0.15
Large	0.35

Table 3: Multiple Linear Regression Analysis (stepwise).

Predictors: Forgiveness and its dimensions

Criterion: Life Satisfaction (Y₁).

Predictor Variable(s)	Unstandardized β	Multiple R	R^2	R^2 Change	Cohen's f^2	F	Sig.
Forgiveness		(Model	$Y_2 = a + \beta_2 X_2 + \beta_1 X_1$)				
X ₂	.201	.204	.042	.042	.04	10.34	.01
X ₁	.180	.278	.077	.036	.08	9.927	.01
Constant	16.323						

X₂=Others Forgiveness, X₁=Self Forgiveness

In table 3 forgiveness and its' dimensions were considered as predictors and life satisfaction as criterion to prepare a regression model. The dimension entitled *Others Forgiveness* accounted for a significant amount of variance in life satisfaction, $R^2=0.042$, $F(1, 238)= 10.34$, $p <0.001$. It can be inferred that the dimension entitled *Others Forgiveness* explaining 4.2% variance in life satisfaction of college students. there exists enough evidence to conclude that the slope of the population regression line is not zero and, hence, that *Others Forgiveness* (forgiveness) is useful predictor of life satisfaction of college students. Further, Cohen's effect size value ($f^2 = 0.04$) suggested a small to medium strength of association between *Others Forgiveness* and life satisfaction. In table 3 it was also found that the another dimension entitled *Self Forgiveness* (Forgiveness) emerged as significant predictor and both the dimensions together accounted for a significant amount of variance in life satisfaction, $R^2=0.077$, $F(1, 237)= 9.927$, $p <0.001$. It can be inferred that the both the dimensions jointly explaining 7.7% variance in life satisfaction of college students. Further, Cohen's effect size value ($f^2 = 0.08$) suggested a small to medium strength of association between *Self Forgiveness* and life satisfaction. The research indicates that the ability to forgive one's self for past offenses can lead to decrease feeling of negative emotions such as *shame and guilt*, and can increase the use of more positive practices such as self-kindness and self-compassion (Cornish and Wade, 2015). These all activities are somewhat leading factors of life satisfaction in the individual. Cornish and Wade (2015) study of a specific research suggests that the ability to truly forgive one's self can be significantly beneficial to an individual's emotional as well as mental well being. The emotional wellbeing and mental wellbeing are segments of wellbeing so that these are also an indicator of satisfaction with life. It means that people having positive feeling followed by forgiveness expected to enjoy better life satisfaction. Therefore, hypothesis "**H2: There will be positive role of forgiveness on life satisfaction**" is supported at the 0.01 level of significance.

Table 4: shows the mean difference of forgiveness and life satisfaction among male and female college students.

Group Statistics								
Variables	Groups	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Mean	Error	t-value	Sig.
Forgiveness	Male	161	71.81	9.099	.717	1.013		.312
	Female	79	70.54	9.041	1.017			
Life Satisfaction	Male	161	24.94	5.431	.428	1.034		.302
	Female	79	24.15	5.745	.646			

The table 4 shows mean differences of forgiveness and life satisfaction among male and female college students, it was found that male and female college students are not differ in terms of forgiveness and life satisfaction. Cornish and Wade (2015) conducted a specific research which suggests that the ability to genuinely forgive one's self can be significantly beneficial to an individual's emotional as well as mental well being; it also an indicator/contributor to lead life satisfaction. Forgiveness either related to oneself, others or situational it is a prime source of satisfaction for the concerned individual. On the other hand adjustment of home/family members, social, emotional, educational or health adjustment itself these all are facilitator of satisfaction with life. So, one should be conscious about the different areas of adjustment as well as must try to develop tendency of forgiveness since related to oneself, others and as per the requirement of the situation.

5. CONCLUSIONS

Consequently, we can irrespectively say that forgiveness positively associated with life satisfaction. It means that those who are used to forgive or having forgiveness tendency will be satisfied with their life on the other hand people with unforgiveness tendency might be less satisfied with their life. Apart from this, in fact life satisfaction is a combination of different factors; forgiveness is one factor of them because as we found that forgiveness contributes only 4 to 7 percent to the life satisfaction. It means that other factors are also playing very crucial role in life satisfaction.

Referring to the aims and objectives of the study and the obtained findings pertaining to the hypotheses and the data analysis, the following conclusions were drawn:

- **Hypothesis 1:** *There will positive relationship between forgiveness and life satisfaction.* This hypothesis is supported because the results revealed that the forgiveness positively and significantly correlated with life satisfaction.

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- **Hypothesis 2:** *There is positive role of forgiveness on life satisfaction.* This hypothesis is also supported. The obtained result shows that forgiveness is significantly contributing to the life satisfaction.
- **Hypothesis 3:** *There will mean difference of forgiveness and life satisfaction among male and female college students.* This hypothesis is not supported because male and female students are insignificantly differs in terms of forgiveness as well as life satisfaction.

Implications

This study pertains college students. As we know that this is a fast-paced world in which changes are taking place tremendously. Accordingly, the overall change related to the environment in which they live and the strategies they adopt to cope with a challenging environment is a major issue before them. Because of the prevailing wide-spread disturbances, their life is filled with the perception of uncertainty yet they have to adjust whatsoever they are facing in their daily lives to be satisfied. There is evident from the obtained findings of the present study that the satisfaction with life is significantly related and affected by forgiveness. They were found comparatively better in life satisfaction those who have the forgiveness tendency. Steps should be taken to adopt the strategies by which the peace can be maintained in life so that the people can flourish in their lives. So far the life satisfaction issue is concerned it can be tackled with the help of involvement of counselors, clinical psychologists and psychiatrists; who can make direction for the better adjustment. Furthermore, the challenge coping strategies should be introduced so that one can adjust with different circumstances. Importance of forgiveness should be introduced, as many studies have shown that forgiveness leads to feeling of happiness and it is also a factor of life satisfaction. In addition, the teachers since the schools should be empowered as a part of the school curriculum to identify the adjustment problems of the students; so that they can develop skills to deal with those obstacles. Finally, we as human beings start to learn by observing our elders' actions so that elders should first bring forgiveness in practice which will be inspirational for the youngsters. Parents are advised to discuss everyday events that happen in their children's life and share their own experiences also to teach them that when and what to do. Doing so, the youngsters might learn many coping strategies to face daily life problems for the better life.

Limitations and Suggestions for future research

As we know that research is an endless process and it is also true that no research is the final solution to any problem. The present research is not an exception because this is also confined to a set of only two variables i.e. forgiveness and life satisfaction. However, life satisfaction itself is a very important variable and need of the human being. It is very crucial to handle all the issues related to any population in a very specific amount of time. Hence, only 240 college students were drawn from Aligarh Muslim University, India campus. The sample size, geographical area and age group should be enhanced for the more precise results so that one can generalize and validate on a larger population.

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